

Blunt Abdominal Trauma Complicated by Intestinal Perforation: Diagnostic and Therapeutic Issues

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Abstract

Introduction: Intestinal perforation after blunt abdominal trauma is rare but potentially fatal. It can progress quietly to the development of stercoral peritonitis, a serious surgical emergency.

Case report: A 31-year-old female patient with no prior history presented with fever and abdominal pain six days after a road traffic accident. CT scan revealed a small bowel perforation with pelvic collection. Resection of the necrotic loop with a double-barrel ileostomy was performed.

Discussion: This case report highlights the diagnostic complexity of post-traumatic intestinal injuries and underscores the seriousness of infectious complications associated with delayed management.

Conclusion: Careful monitoring after abdominal trauma, combined with early imaging, is essential to prevent progression to diffuse peritonitis.

Introduction

Blunt abdominal trauma is a common cause of emergency department visits. While liver or splenic injuries are the most common, intestinal perforation remains rare (1 to 5%) but particularly serious due to the risk of peritoneal contamination. The clinical course can be insidious, and a free interval of several days is often observed, complicating the diagnosis. We report a case of blunt abdominal trauma complicated by intestinal perforation.

Case Presentation

This is a 31-year-old female patient with no particular medical history who was the victim of a road traffic accident following a collision between two vehicles. The trauma involved several body regions, including the

head, thorax, abdomen, and pelvis, without loss of consciousness or initial vomiting. The patient's course was silent for six days, after which the patient developed diffuse abdominal pain, predominantly hypogastric, associated with food vomiting and an unmeasured fever. On admission, she was conscious (GCS 15/15), hemodynamically and respiratory stable (BP 130/80 mmHg, HR 85 bpm, RR 18 c/min, T° 38 °C), with normal conjunctiva. Abdominal examination revealed generalized guarding with hypogastric echymosis and an old Pfannenstiel incision.

No signs of perforation were found on digital rectal examination. Abdominopelvic CT scan performed on the 7th post-traumatic day revealed a small bowel perforation at the right pelvic level, associated with a

More Information

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Blunt abdominal trauma, intestinal perforation, bowel injury, emergency laparotomy, diagnostic delay.

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large adjacent collection of 100 x 113 mm, as well as a bilateral fracture of the iliac wings with left gluteal hematoma.

Figure 1: Hypogastric Ecchymosis

Figure 2: Abdominal Pelvic CT Scan Revealing Small Bowel Perforation

The biological assessment showed significant hyperleukocytosis (32,770/mm³), a very high CRP at 320 mg/L, hemoglobin at 13.1 g/dL and normal lipase levels. After multidisciplinary advice (neurosurgery, orthopedics, thoracic), the patient was taken to the operating room urgently. A midline laparotomy above and below the umbilical cord was performed under general anesthesia. Surgical exploration revealed a stercoral and purulent peritoneal effusion located in the pelvis, blocked by the greater omentum and the sigmoid loop. Extensive necrosis of the small intestine over a length of 20 to 30 cm from 30 cm from the ileocecal junction was observed, without involvement of the rectum, colon, pancreas or diaphragm. Resection

of the necrotic segment was performed, followed by the creation of a double-barrel ileostomy. Peritoneal cleansing with saline (8 L) and pelvic drainage completed the procedure.

Figure 3: Intraoperative Image Showing Spleen Necrosis

The immediate postoperative course was marked by clinical stability.

Discussion

Blunt abdominal trauma, often observed in road traffic accidents, constitutes a real diagnostic challenge, especially in cases of occult digestive injuries. Among these, small bowel perforation remains rare - estimated at less than 5% of cases - but particularly serious due to the high risk of stercoral peritonitis, which can rapidly be life-threatening [1,2]. The injury mechanism generally relies on crushing of the small bowel between the abdominal wall and the spine, leading to parietal ischemia, mesenteric contusion, or even delayed rupture of the intestinal wall [3]. This dynamic explains the occurrence of a "free interval", characterized by an initial asymptomatic or pauci-symptomatic period, as observed in our patient. This delay is tricky, because it can mask the progression to severe peritonitis [4]. Clinically, the diagnosis is based on often subtle signs: increasing abdominal pain, vomiting, fever, or even subocclusion. Physical examination may remain of little help in the first hours, which reduces the sensitivity of isolated clinical diagnosis [5]. Imaging, in particular abdominal CT scan with injection of contrast agent, plays a central role today. It allows the detection of indirect signs such as pneumoperitoneum, intraperitoneal effusion, digestive thickening or even the presence of intra-abdominal collections [6,7]. In our observation, CT was decisive in visualizing the perforation and directing surgical management without delay. The occurrence of stercoral peritonitis represents a critical evolutionary turning point. This complication is linked to the massive diffusion of fecal contents into the peritoneal cavity, leading to a high risk of severe sepsis, multi-organ failure and mortality,

which can reach 50% according to some series [8,9]. Management is based on emergency surgery: resection of the necrotic or perforated intestinal segment, fecal diversion by stoma in the event of inflammatory conditions unfavorable to anastomosis, abundant peritoneal lavage, and effective drainage [10]. In our case, a double-barrel ileostomy was preferred given the context of advanced peritonitis. This strategy, often adopted in high-risk situations, reduces the occurrence of anastomotic fistulas and postoperative infections [11]. Finally, the prognosis depends closely on the precocity of the diagnosis, the severity of peritoneal contamination, the initial clinical state, as well as the quality of multidisciplinary management. This observation highlights the importance of prolonged monitoring after abdominal trauma, even in the absence of initial suggestive signs.

Conclusion

Post-traumatic small bowel perforation is a surgical emergency that is difficult to diagnose, particularly in the presence of a free interval. The resulting stercoral peritonitis represents a severe developmental milestone, requiring rapid, multidisciplinary management. Clinical vigilance, early imaging, and appropriate surgical intervention are the cornerstones of a favorable prognosis.

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